

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The potential of radio programs in addressing infertility and other maternal health issues amongst married couples in Isiala-Ngwa North LGA of Abia State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper takes a deep look into two of the major challenges some couples in Isiala-Ngwa North Local Government Area of Abia State face in their journey of marriage such as; infertility and the inability to make good choices on mode of child birth. Infertility is classified into two major categories: the primary and secondary infertility. Whereas the former is when a couple cannot procreate naturally within the first one year of their trial, the latter refers to when a couple finds it difficult to conceive after they had experienced conception due to health challenges. The inability to make good choices on mode of child delivery is a big challenge in Isiala-Ngwa North. Some couples who were lucky to pass through the gestational period within the first one year of their marriage or even after they have had a baby before, end up topping the chart of child or mother and child mortality due to some unjustifiable belief about some certain modes of child birth. Hence, there is the need to know how radio programs can help those in the medical line in salvaging the situation as whatever that directly or indirectly affects the family, affects the society. Moreover, it considers different approaches the radio can take in unveiling important information on fertility enhancement and prenatal programs to their audience, and persuading the intending and married couples into taking the right steps and at the right time. Sampling and descriptive methods were used, where five hundred questionnaires were dispatched to ten different communities in the rural areas of Isiala-Ngwa North LGA of Abia State such as Ihie, Umuakwu, Okpualangwa, Nbawsi, Amaoji, Umuosu, Mbubo, Umuala, Owerrinta and Ntigha to ascertain how effective the radio stations in Abia have been fairs in the sensitization and dissemination of child birth and infertility related topics having known the challenges it poses on families and the extent they have gone in proffering solution. 480 of the questionnaires were returned and it was discovered that even though many of the respondents have access to radio more than they have to hospitals, they do not have access to adequate information on marital and fertility related issues.

Keywords: Infertility; Radio; Programs; Public Health

1. Introduction

Infertility no doubt is a disease of the male or female reproductive system that results to the failure to achieve a pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular unprotected sex [1]. According to [2] infertility is a *significant* public health challenge that poses a multidimensional problem to Economic, Social, and cultural activities of man. It has embattled so many families both in the time past and in the present. [3] Stated that up to 12-15% of couples are unable to conceive after trying to get pregnant for one year due to health challenges. It has also been established by UN report that infertility is on the rise from 5-10% in 2020, as there was an average of five children per woman world-wide as at 1950 but an average of two children per woman world-wide in 2022 [4].

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Infertility be it Primary; where a couple could not conceive for their first one year after solemnization or Secondary; where a couple cannot conceive naturally after they had experienced conception as classified by [2], can either be caused by the health status of the male partner, female partner or both hence the need for prevention through different approaches and methods [5], and the transmission of educational programs on infertility and public health campaign within and outside Abia state through the radio is one of the viable approaches.

According to [6] on the list of radio stations in Nigeria, a minimum of 14 radio stations exist in Abia State with 7 of them situated in Umuahia the state capital, and the other 7 located in Aba the economic city. That is to say that the major radio stations in Abia State are situated in the main hob cities of the state and their environs with just few located in other areas. Moreover, Isiala-Ngwa North is one of the 17 local Government areas of Abia State, Nigeria [7].

Therefore, the importance or role of Radio in reaching out to the greater number of its audience of different ages, gender, location, status, religion, and so on at the same time can never be ignored. Even though we are in the internet age, Radio still rules the world as Forty Four Thousand radio Stations broadcast to five billion people, or roughly 70% of the world as stated by [8].

Furthermore, a critical look at: Abia family love 99.9 FM. [9] Umuahia, BUZZ 89.7FM. [10]Aba, and BCA 88. 1 FM. [11] Umuahia week-long programs schedule as shown in Table 1, can be a sample or an eye opener to the extent Isiala-Ngwa reaching radio stations have not given sufficient attention to family or public health campaign and propagation hence the awakening call through this research.

Table 1 A week-long Programs schedule of Some Radio Stations in within the reach of Isiala-Ngwa Residents

S / N	Radio Station	Time Programs						
		Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
1	Love FM	04:30 Soft inspirational songs						
		05:00 Morning Flight	04:45 Morning Flight	04:45 Morning Flight	04:45 Morning Flight	04:45 Morning Flight	05:00 Saturday morning Therapy	05:00 Music
		06:00 Commercials	06:00 Commercials	06:00 Music	06:00 Commercials	06:00 Wake up Call	06:00 Music	06:00 Commercials
		06:30 Major News	06:30 Pidgin News	06:30 English News				
		06:45 Sports Classic	06:45 Music	06:45 Music				
		07:00 Omnibus	07:00 Omnibus	07:00 Omnibus	07:00 Omnibus	07:00 Music	07:00 Sports Classic	07:00 The Ministration
		08:00 Newspaper Review	07:30 Music	08:00 Lift up Your Heart				
		09:00 Open Parliament	08:45 News at the hour	08:45 Music	09:00 Open Parliament	08:45 Music	08:00 Newspaper Review	09:00 Thanksgiving/Testimony
		10:00 News at the hour	09:00 Open Parliament	09:00 Open Parliament	10:00 News at the hour	09:00 Open Parliament	08:45 *Health Matters	10:00 Praise Time
		10:05 DJ time out	10:00 News at the hour	09:55 News at the hour	10:05 Late Morning Cruise	10:00 News at the hour	09:45 How Your Area	11:00 Favorite Bible Verse

12:00 Pidgin News	10:05 Late Morning Cruise	10:05 Late Morning Cruise	11:00 Shine Your Eyes	10:05 Late Morning Cruise	10:30 Kiddies Time Out	12:00 Major Pidgin News
13:15 Oldies	11:00 OUK Speaks	11:00 Talking Point	11:30 Healing Words from the master	10:30 SEN. T.A. Orji Health Talk	11:00 Campus Gist	12:30 Hospitality Time
13:00 Political Aproko	12:00 Major Pidgin News	12:00 Major Pidgin News	11:55 Major Pidgin News	11:00 From the Assembly	12:00 Major News	13:30 How WakaforChurch
14:00 Enter Market	12:15 Oldies	12:15 Oldies	12:15 Oldies	12:00 Pidgin News	12:30 Saturday Jolly	14:30 Music
15:00 AkukoUwa	13:00 Political Aproko	13:00 NaijaTatafo	13:00 Political Aproko	12:20 Oldies	13:30 Music	15:00 Abu Otito
15:15 Igbo News Paper Review	15:00 AkukoUwa	14:00 Mixed Music (DJ)	14:00 Igbos love Themselves	13:00 Political Aproko	14:00 Copa Shun	15:30 Jawayanma
15:30 Okwundinaehiodo	15:15 Music	14:30 Peoples Events and Places	15:00 AkukoUwa	14:00 Mixed Music (DJ)	14:30 NaijaTatafo	16:00 NriMkpuru Obi
16:15 Music	15:30 Okwundinaehiodo	15:00 AkukoUwa	15:15 Music	14:30 Peoples Events and Places	15:30 NdiNne "Ma Ma"	16:30 Abu Ekele
16:30 OkwuNtabire	16:00 Music	15:15 Igbo News Paper Review	15:30 Okwundinaehiodo	15:30 AkukoUwa	16:30 Music	17:00 Speak Igbo (Suwakwa Igbo)
17:00 Traffic Wahala	16:30 Qwam, Qwam	15:30 Okwundinaehiodo	16:15 AkukonaEgwu	15:15 KupuNkwa	17:00 AkukonaEgwu	18:00 Major News
18:00 Major News	17:00 Traffic Wahala	16:15 AharaNdu	16:30 Igbo Ezue	15:30 Okwundinaehiodo	17:30 Akpakwalam Ochi	18:20 PPA(Music)

		18:30 Complete football	18:00 English News	16:30 Onatokaifo	16:55 Traffic Wahala	16:15 Music	18:00 Major News	18:30 Peoples Events and Places
		19:00 Deeper Life	18:30 Complete football	16:45 KupuNkwa	17:55 Major News	16:25 UgboEkele	18:20 Music	19:00 Music
		20:30 Music	19:00 Talk your own Naija	16:55 Traffic Wahala	18:20 Complete football	17:00 Traffic Wahala	19:00 Pastors on Fire	20:00 How was Your Sunday
		21:00 Praise Time	19:30 Music	18:00 Major News	18:55 Top 10	18:00 Major News	20:30 Music	20:45 Hour of Fresh Anointing
		21:30 How has Your Day Been	20:00 Ogre NdiNturuObia	18:30 Mid-Week Sports	20:00 Throw Back Thursday	18:30 Complete football	21:00 Praise Time	21:00 Praise Time
		22:30 Love Serenades (22:30)	21:00 Praise Time	19:30 Music	21:00 Praise Time	19:00 Exclusive Friday	21:30 Saturday Night Show	21:30 How was Your Sunday
			21:30 Upcoming and Trending	20:00 Complete Woman	21:30 Reggae Talawa	20:00 Gentle Men Corner		22:30 Music
			23:30 Music Serenades	21:00 Praise Time	22:00 Ikoro (Igbo Belt)	21:00 Praise Time		23:00 Soul Serenade
				21:30 Music	23:00 UgboIhunanya	21:30 Goody Bag		
				22:00 Revelation		22:30 TGIF Night Show		
				23:00 Music				
2	BCA	04:58 Drum Signal	04:58 Drum Signal	04:58 Drum Signal	04:45 Drum Signal	04:58 Drum Signal	04:58 Drum Signal	4:58 Drum Signal

05:00 Opening formalities and prayer						
05:20 Daybreak Cruise	05:20 UnuAbọọla Chi	05:20 Midweek Safari	05:15 88-At-Dawn (contd.)	05:15 Weekend Sports	05:20 Una Morning o-o	05:15 Organ Music
06:00 Angelus	06:00 Angelus	06:00 Angelus	05:20 Free Pray	06:00 Angelus	06:00 Angelus	05:30 Thanks and Praises
06:02 News Digest	06:02 News Digest	06:02 News Digest	06:00 Angelus	06:02 News Digest	06:02 News Digest	06:00 Angelus
06:05 PSA/Commercials	06:05 Free Pray	06:05 Free Pray	06:02 News Digest	06:05 Free Pray	06:05 Free Pray	06:02 News Digest
06:30 News/Commentary	06:30 News/Commentary	06:30 News / Commentary	05:05 PSA/Commercials	06:30 News / Commentary	06:30 News / Commentary	06:05 PSA/Commercials
07:00 FRCN News	07:00 FRCN News	07:00 FRCN News	06:30 News / Commentary	07:00 FRCN News	07:00 FRCN News	07:00 FRCN News
07:45 Executive Diary	07:45 88-At-Dawn (contd.)	07:45 Executive Diary	07:00 FRCN News	07:45 Executive Diary	07:45 Free Pray	07:30 Power to Excel
08:00 News Digest	08:00 News Digest	08:00 News Digest	07:45 Assembly in Action	08:00 News Digest	08:00 News Digest	07:45 Daily Guide
08:05 Daybreak Cruise(contd)	08:05 Oyorima	08:05 NgwugwuIhunanya (Commercial)	08:00 News Digest	08:05 Surugedee	08:02 OnwuagaOnwuaga (Sponsored)	08:00 News Digest
08:45 OcheOchichi	09:00 AkukoUwa/okwunaeso Akiko	09:00 AkukoUwa/okwunaeso Akiko	08:05 Free Pray	09:00 AkukoUwa/okwunaeso Akiko	09:00 AkukoUwa/okwunaeso Akiko	08:05 Let's Worship

09:00 AkukoUwa/ okwunaeso Akiko	09:30 Sports Challenge	09:30 Free Pray	08:30 ½ Hour of Help (Sponsored)	09:30 OcheOchichi	09:20 Free Pray	09:00 AkukoUwa
09:30 EkeleUmuibe(Com mercial)	10:00 News Digest	10:00 News Digest	09:00 AkukoUwa/ okwunaeso Akiko	09:45 ASOPADEC FILE (Sponsored)	09:30 N’uloNzuko	09:30 Abu Di Ichelche
10:00 News Digest	10:05 Free Pray	10:05 AjuoAzaa	09:30 Free Pray	10:00 News Digest	09:45 EgwuAgwaraOgwa	10:00 News Digest
10:05 KamKwuo (Phone- in)	10:30 K’anyiNoria	10:45 Odenjiji (Rpt)	10:00 News Digest	10:05 Moving Train	10:00 News Digest	10:05 Abu Ofufe
11:00 News Digest	11:00 News Digest	11:00 News Digest	10:05 Otigba	11:00 News Digest	10:05 Mega Sports	11:00 News Digest
11:05 ASOPADEC File English (Sponsored)	11:05 Heart to Heart (Commercial)	11:05 Business Connection (Sponsored)	11:00 News Digest	11:05 Free Pray	10:30 ¼ Hour Word Encounter	11:05 Jisie Ike
11:30 Free Pray	12:00 News Digest	11:30 Wesley Time (Sponsored)	11:05 Free Pray	12:00 News Digest	10:45 Odenjiji (Sponsored)	12:00 News Digest
12:00 News Digest	12:05 Groove Train	12:00 News Digest	12:05 Groove Train	12:05 Naija Salute	11:00 World News/ Commentary	12:05 Gospel Menu
12:05 Groove Train	13:00 World News/ Commentary	12:05 Star of the Week	13:00 World News/ Commentary	13:00 World News/ Commentary	11:30 Voice of Light (Sponsored)	13:00 World News/ Commentary
13:00 World News/ Commentary	14:00 News Digest	13:00 World News/ Commentary	13:30 Free Play	13:30 Let’s Share	12:00 News Digest	13:30 Concert Half Hour
13:30 Free Play	14:05 Free Play	13:30 Free Play	14:00 News Digest	14:00 News Digest	12:05 Choose and Rock	14:00 News Digest

13:45 Short story	14:30 Living Spring Time (Sponsored)	14:00 News Digest	14:05 From Me To You (Commercial)	14:05 Now Sound (Sponsored)	13:00 World News/ Commentary	14:05 Sunday Rendezvous(Com mercial)
14:00 News Digest	15:00 News Digest	14:05 Free Play	15:00 News Digest	15:00 News Digest	13:30 Free Play	15:00 News Digest
14:05 Brain Teaser	15:05 Press Review/Nchikotaa kwukwoakuko	14:30 Bizarre World	15:05 Press Review/Nchikotaa kwukwoakuko	15:05 Press Review/Nchikotaa kwukwoakuko	13:45 The Beautiful Word (Sponsored)	15:05 Press Review/Nchikotaa kwukwoakuko
15:05 News Digest	15:30 Wind From Heaven (Sponsored)	15:00 News Digest	15:30 College Debate	15:30 The Kitchen	14:00 News Digest	15:30 Divine Mercy
15:05 Press Review/Nchikotaa kwukwoakuko	16:00 FRCN News	15:05 Press Review/Nchikotaa kwukwoakuko	16:00 FRCN News	16:00 FRCN News	14:05 Reggae Dance Hall	15:45 Christ Embassy
15:30 School's Quiz	16:30 Story Story	15:30 BBC/WST-Radio Youth Show-Flva	16:30 Wisdom And Deeper Sense(sponsored)	16:30 Box Show (sponsored)	14:30 Preaching The Truth (Sponsored)	16:00 FRCN News
16:00 FRCN News	17:00 News Digest	16:00 FRCN News	17:00 News Digest	17:00 News Digest	15:00 News Digest	16:30 Kiddies View
16:30 IsiyiNkeNdu (sponsored)	17:05 Men's Round Table	16:30 Midweek Sports	17:05 Talk Back	17:05 Wedding Bells(commercial)	15:05 Press Review/Nchikotaa kwukwoakuko	17:00 News Digest
17:00 News Digest	17:30 Zion Train	17:00 News Digest	17:30 B.B.C. Talk Your Own	18:00 News/Commentar y	15:30 Sports Extra	17:05 Golden Hymns

17:05 Your Health	18:00 News/Commentary	17:05 Showcase (Free Play)	17:45 Free Play	18:30 Junior World	16:00 FRCN News	18:00 News/Commentary
17:30 Christ Embassy	18:30 Youth Panorama	17:30 Free Play	18:00 News/Commentary	19:05 Free Play	16:30 Family Focus	18:30 The Lord's Chosen Message
18:00 BCA News/Commentary	19:30 Mass Literacy (Sponsored)	18:00 News/Commentary	18:30 Nkuzi Igbo	19:30 ½ Hour of Possibilities	17:00 News Digest	19:00 News Digest
18:30 News Conference	20:00 AkukoUwa/Okwu N'esoAkuko	18:30 Issues Of The Moment	19:30 ½ Hour of Consolation (Sponsored)	20:00 AkukoUwa/Okwu N'esoAkuko	17:05 Una Well Don(Commercial)	19:25 NriUche
19:05 Free Play	20:30 Ezinulo	19:05 Free Play	20:00 AkukoUwa/Okwu N'esoAkuko	20:30 Squadron Football Highway	17:30 Free Play	19:30 Victory ½ Hour (Sponsored)
19:30 Back to the Bible	21:00 News/Commentary	19:45 Free Play	20:30 ADP Radio Farmer	21:00 News/Commentary	18:00 News/Commentary	20:00 AkukoUwa/Okwu N'esoAkuko
20:00 AkukoUwa/Okwu N'esoAkuko	21:30 Free Play	20:00 AkukoUwa/Okwu N'esoAkuko	21:30 InyomEzuo	21:30 Christ Embassy	18:30 In Touch with God (sponsored)	20:30 MepeeAkwukwoNsoGi (Sponsored)
20:30 Nti Nara Rie	22:00 FRCN News	20:30 The Voice of EL (Sponsored)	22:00 FRCN News	22:00 FRCN News	19:00 Akukosin'imeobodo	21:00 News/Commentary
21:00 News/Commentary	22:30 Free Play	21:00 News/Commentary	22:30 Free Play	22:30 Free Play	19:30 Healing Words from the master	21:30 Free Play
21:30 Free Play	23:00 News Digest	21:30 Bangaskiya Krista (Sponsored)	23:00 News Digest	23:00 News Digest	20:00 AkukoUwa/Okwu N'esoAkuko	22:00 FRCN News
22:00	23:05	22:00	23:05	23:05	20:30	22:30

		FRCN News	Jazz Splash	FRCN News	Naija Beats	Closing Ranks	UgboNdioma(Com mercial)	Sunday Night Links
		22:30 Free Play	23:55 Closing Formalities	22:30 Free Play	23:55 Closing Formalities	23:55 Closing Formalities	21:00 News/Commentar y	23:00 News Digest
		23:00 News Digest	00:00 Close Down	23:00 News Digest	00:00 Close Down	00:00 Close Down	21:30 Free Play	23:05 Sunday Night Links (Contd)
		23:05 Bedtime Serenade		23:05 Bedtime Serenade			22:00 FRCN News	23:55 Closing Formalities
		23:55 Closing Formalities		23:55 Closing Formalities			22:30 Free Play	00:00 Close Down
		00:00 Close Down		00:00 Close Down			23:00 News Digest	
							23:05 What's up	
							11:55 Closing Formalities	
							00:00 Close Down	
3	Buz z FM	06:00 Buzz Fast	06:00 – 08:00 Buzz Fast	06:00 – 08:00 Buzz Fast	08:00 – 09:00 Buzz Fast	04:30 – 07:30 Hard Talk	01:30 – 06:30 Hard Talk	03:00 – 20:30 Hard Talk
		09:00 Hard Talk	07:30 – 10:30 Hard Talk	08:00 – 09:00 KpakpakpaTatafo	08:00 – 09:00 KpakpakpaTatafo	08:00 - 09:00 KpakpakpaTatafo	08:00 – 9:00 KpakpakpaTatafo	Buzz Gbedu Corner 12:00 – 18:00
		15:30 – 19:00 Buzz Gbedu Corner	08:00 - 09:00 KpakpakpaTatafo	08:00 – 09:00 People's Parliament	08:00 – 09:00 People's Parliament	08:00 – 09:00 People's Parliament	08:00 – 09:00 People's Parliament	18:30 – 23:30 Music Mix

	23:30 Music Mix	08 – 9:00 People’s Parliament	13:30 – 15:30 Hard Talk	22:30 – 23:30 Hard Talk	12:00 – 20:30 Buzz Gbedu Corner	12:00 – 20:30 Buzz Gbedu Corner	
		04:30 – 10:00 Buzz Gbedu Corner	20:00 – 22:00 Buzz Gbedu Corner	17:00 – 20:00 Buzz Gbedu Corner	21:00 – 23:30 Music Mix	18:00 – 23:30 Music Mix	
		10:30 – 11:30 Music Mix	22:30 – 11:30 Music Mix	20:30 – 23:30 Music Mix			

The above program schedules and its likes no doubt enlightens listeners but does not capture family important and sensitive programs like infertility and maternity or even other marital issues as desired.

In this study, the following research questions guided the study:

- How is the reach of Abia Radio Stations to Isiala-Ngwa North People?
- Health and current affairs, which is more broadcasted by Abia radio stations?
- What is the percentage of couples who were pre informed about infertility and maternal issues through the radio before marriage?
- How many couples have gotten a hint or a lead way to their infertility solution through a radio program?
- How many couples are infertile or have experienced child or child and mother mortality due to lack of information?

Moreover, [12] stated that “The power of radio is not that it speaks to millions, but that it speaks intimately and privately to each one of those millions”.

Radio is very effective in speaking to people’s minds and its usage in the prevention and management of infertility would not be a bad idea as the extent to which radio can contribute to improving the livelihood situation of its listeners is yet to be well documented. Marriage is one of the sacred values of Igbo culture and it is very crucial in the life and advancement of any given society as it precedes fertility, infertility and other maternal health issues [13. 14]

Myths, rumors and or grapevine should not be totally overlooked or ignored but should be erased or subdued by giving out the right information and at the right time so as not to create an avenue for it to thrive and the radio can be a good tool in persuading the people in learning and unlearning [15]

Infertility is fairly common and can be a difficult situation for individuals and couples diagnosed after having frequent and unprotected coitus for one year or more without conception. It is a situation that can affect both male and female partners because infertility is nearly as common in men as it is in women [3]. 15% of couples are estimated to have problem of conception, 48 million couples and 186 million individuals experience infertility globally while one out of four couples in the developing countries is affected by infertility [16- 18].

Moreso, according to [3], the primary reason for most divorce among couples is as a result of infertility.

2. Materials and Methods

The method used is an in-depth evaluation method, using participatory approach that involves tuning in to many Abia radio stations from the sample areas, field visit, analysis, and desk study of other related studies already carried out. The major technique used in the collection of data is questionnaires, interviews and observation.

The investigation covered amongst others, 10 communities in Isiala-Ngwa North LGA such as; Ihie, umuakwu, okpualangwa, Nbawsi, Amaoji, Umuosu, Mbubo, Umuala, Owerrinta and Ntigha, where an average of 50 homes were visited in each community. A total number of 500 questionnaires were distributed to married couples and in most cases where the couples are not lettered; interviews alongside discussions in their local Ngwa dialect were used.

Data gathered through interviews, questionnaires and observation reviewed specifically how effective Abia radio stations have been on broadcasting marriage, infertility, and other maternal health related programs in Isiala-Ngwa North.

3. Results

The result of the survey is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Couples' Access to Radio and their Level of Awareness on Issues of Infertility

SN	Causes of Infertility and Maternal Health Issues.	Percentage Response				
		SD	D	SLA	A	SA
1	My radio receives Abia radio Stations Signals	0	0	4	6	90
2	I have access to radio more than I do to hospitals	1	3	2	4	90
3	I have listened to Infertility/Maternity Programs on radio	60	20	10	5	1
4	I gave birth to the total number of children I desire	70	10	5	2	3
5	I have been affected by infertility	3	10	5	2	70
6	I know Caesarean section to be a demeaning mode of birth.	2	5	7	24	65
7	A man can cause infertility	20	40	30	4	6
8	Infertility can be cured without visiting hospitals	30	5	5	10	50

SD, D, SLA, A, SA means Strongly Disagreed, Disagreed, Slightly Agreed, Agreed, and Strongly Agreed respectively.

4. Discussions

4.1. The Reach of Abia Radio Stations to Isiala-Ngwa North:

From Table 2 above, 90% of our respondents strongly agreed (SA) that they get full signal of not less than 11 radio stations in their homes which means that if all the radio stations utilize their reach to Isiala-Ngwa people in broadcasting fertility and maternal related programs to their audience, it will go a long way in cubing the infertility trend notwithstanding that 4 and 6% slightly agreed (SLA) and agreed (A) respectively to Abia radio stations signals' reach to them.

Moreso, there is unarguable great competition amongst Abia Radio stations which makes their programs to be designed on topical issues that endears their listeners to them. They also have good on-air personalities with great fan base that have the prowess to keep their audience glued to them and their programs. Nonetheless, it was observed and from table 1 sample above that Abia radio programs dwell more on the following:

- 50% of current affairs where you get programs like newspaper headlines, a compilation of resent events.
- 20% of political interviews and analysis
- 10% of entertainment programs where you get sports programs, birthday calls, music and other forms of entertainment talks.
- 10% of religious programs where you get sermons, prayers, and other forms of religious programs and
- 5% of relationship programs where the topic of discussion can be anything depending on the presenter. With this information, much is left to be desired on health related issues as couples only get such information through radio product advertisements.

4.2. Accessibility to Radio Programs Over Hospitals:

From Table 2, 90% of married couples residing in Isiala-Ngwa North strongly Agreed (SA) that they have access to Abia radio stations' programs more than they do to hospitals. Whereas they rarely visit hospitals, all the 50 households visited in each community have access to a radio set in the form of digital, the analogue or they even use their cell phones to get connected. Although 1, 3, 2, and 4% of the respondents strongly disagreed (SD) disagreed (D) slightly agreed (SLA) and agreed (A) respectively to their Abia radio programs accessibility, it will indeed be a good idea to get Isiala-Ngwa North couples exposed to marriage, infertility, and other maternal related issues programs through the radio.

4.3. Infertility As A Result Of Insufficient Access to Related Information:

Form the data collated, it is discovered that 60% of the respondents are ignorant of infertility to be a health related issue. Those who are affected consider their situation to have been engineered by their neighbors or enemies through voodoo or to have been caused by their past life without going for diagnosis. Instead, they move from one prayer house to another in search of solution. After some interviews and conversations, it was discovered that couples in Isiala-Ngwa North consider prayer houses to be more effective in handling infertility and other maternal health related issues over hospitals which can only be corrected through persuasion and proper direction. The radio can do just fine when employed in addressing some of these issues.

Furthermore, 10% of the respondents slightly agreed (SLA) that they have been informed through the radio ads that infection can cause a couple not to conceive at will and are advised to come to some stands of the product advisers for examinations and medications. 20% disagreed (D) while 5 and 1% agreed (A) and strongly agreed (SA) respectively.

Moreso, after some enlightenment, 75% of the couples were able to accept that their condition can be tagged as infertility and it is so because they were not exposed to the right information before and in marriage.

4.4. Child Birth Satisfaction and Infertility:

This work reviled that secondary infertility is more rampant in the sample area than primary infertility as 70% of the respondents strongly disagreed (SD) that they are satiated by the total number of children they have. Quarrying further, more than 10 couples in each community visited disclosed that they just stopped conceiving naturally when they are still in their reproductive age while they still desire to have more children and cannot tell what the cause is. 10% disagreed (D) owing to the issue surrounding child sex as they may desire to stop but because they are still not okay with child genders they have, they keep on trying in order to get as they desire. While some may succeed, others won't hence polygamy and other marital issues. 5, 2 and 3% slightly agreed (SLA), Agreed (A) and strongly agreed (SD) respectively that they are satiated with the total number of children they've got.

4.5. The Effect of Infertility and Other Maternal Issues:

Aside the general effects of infertility and maternal health issues that can negatively affect the general wellbeing of a person's overall health and quality of life such as divorce, psychiatric symptoms, anxiety and depression, infertile couples in Isiala-Ngwa are really affected uniquely. Many of them, mainly the women as [19] noted that childless women are usually stigmatized, disinherited, isolated and neglected by the entire local Family and community so, they run from one herbal house to another in search of solution where most of them end up being extorted without any positive result. The radio which should have been a better tool in directing and filling the right information gap is doing little or nothing in that regard. Some of the infertile couples have turned to prayer warriors overnight because when the right information is not within, the erroneous ones will thrive as they tag their infertility to be as a result of witchcraft hence the need for prayers. The women are mostly affected as their husbands end up marrying a second wife if no pregnancy is coming forth after a while in their marriage.

Moreso, many have lost their loved ones, their lives and that of their unborn babies because of unjustifiable reasons gotten from ancient tales or grapevine which they hold to high esteem why Cesarean section (CS) are seen as a demeaning mode of child delivery. CS as a mode of child birth is yet to be accepted as a prestigious way to give birth as they disdainfully say "she gave birth through operation, under the knife" followed by the announcement of the sex of the baby even before asking about the status of the mother and child and welcoming them home. It is so serious that some women will even prefer death over C-Section as they will be seen as not being real women, a way to make them feel inferior while those who had natural birth pride in it as the heroines of their clan.

Men on the other hand are also affected as their childlessness affects their ego, giving rise to relationship issues [20]. They as a result, marry more than one wife in search of children and to exonerate themselves even when the fault may be from them. Some about-to-wed men insist that their partners must conceive before they pay their bride price.

Although [5] have stated that the percentage of infertility caused by women is same as causes by men, an average Isiala-Ngwa North husband does not see himself as one who cannot father a child and as such, the blame is always on the women [20]. The men are treated as sacred cows while the women move from one place to another in search of solution which should have been sorted out by both parties. Non can gainsay that health care requires collaboration rooted in trust and respect, best to be cultivated through professionalism [21], but then, infertility has become a global challenge which affects Abia radio stations audience and as such much is required of the radio and health professionals for effective prevention and management as all these can be well addressed through the radio when employed.

5. Conclusion

Conclusively, this research is a call for health personnel, public health activists and radio program managers to maximize their usage of radio in public health campaigns and advocacy. Radio no doubt can do the magic of reaching heterogeneous audience and at the same time. It has been proven to be more accessible, potable and economical amongst other qualities and should be effectively utilized in proffering solutions to family health related issues. Radio having its functions to be giving out timely information, educating and entertaining amongst others should be fully deployed in proffering solution to family and health related matters by giving the right information and disproving the wrong ones, guiding and enlightening the people on maternity issues and how, where and when to get a solution. Isiala-ngwa North people are endeared to their radio gadgets and will live healthier, better and be able to make better choices on family related matters when they are granted the opportunity through their favorite medium as the lettered and non-lettered listen to and rely on the radio for information.

Aside the areas of infertility and maternal health issues, preventive and management measures that can strictly be handled by health professionals such as in vitro fertilization (IVF), cycle based treatments and its likes, there are informative areas the radio can help in salvaging the situation in the following ways:

The radio can inform, educate, and persuade the people to reconsider their views about Cesarean Section as a result of mirth, grapevine and its causes and to accept the procedure as a good and acceptable mode of child birth when recommended by their health advisers.

Emphasize on the need to go for fertility medical examination after their first one year of trying to conceive, if possible, even before marriage instead of moving from one prayer or herbal house to another in search of solution where most of them end up being victims of extortion.

That maternal and infertility issues are more medical than it is to religion.

To collaborate more with public health personals to broadcast more of health and family related issues and the little ways to maintain good fertility such as good hygiene just as they do to current affairs and politics.

To enlighten couples that infertility is not only a feminine thing but a couple's challenge that should be battled or managed collectively. Even though male infertility is a problem that no one admits exits as it is regarded as a taboo hence the practice of polygamy because women are frequently assumed to be the local culprit of infertility in marriages, it is still an existing problem.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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